

Necropolitics and Death-world in William Delisle Hay's *Doom of the Great City*

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Abstract: *Harry Harrison's Deathworld, a 1960 novel imagined a world where humans had to fight death at every turn for survival. The concept of necropolitics views such exposure to death as a form of control. Taking inspiration from these works, an attempt is made here to see how ecological degradation similarly fashions a death-world for humans which takes away their autonomy. It thus underlines the urgency for rethinking human to nature and human to human interactions.*

Keywords: **Biopolitics, Necropolitics, Death-world, sovereignty, Ecocriticism, social ecology**

Michel Foucault remarked that with the coming of biopolitics death is no longer talked about. The 'age of life' only focused on ways to enable living. A challenge to this has emerged in the form of environmental degradation and ecocriticism has enabled conversations around the changing human-environment relationship and its adverse effects. These papers then turns to the representation of an environmental hazard (London smog) in one of the literary works to explore how death-worlds are created in which humans are transformed into the living-dead. It tries to show how the idea of sovereignty has undergone a change as biopolitics is being replaced by necropolitics.

Foucault characterized biopolitics as the attempt to control and regulate population. Here, the government exercises its sovereignty

by trying to maximize the life span of its citizens (Murray 193). Earlier under Roman rule, the father, who was the head of the family, possessed the power to decide on whether his children would live or die (*patria potestas*). This sovereign power was summed up as “to take life or let live” (Murray 197). Stuart Murray observed that this was a society where the constructs of power and life were built around death. Death showcased the existence of life and the sword symbolized this power. This changed with modernity when government devised the policy of taking charge of life by providing the means to sustain it. Hence there arose counting of births, deaths, alongside planning public health, hygiene, welfare, marriage laws etc. There arose a new formula to explain this, “to make live and let die.” Now the individual was part of the state’s population and this is the point at which state makes its entry to put in place new mechanisms of control in the name of well-being. For Foucault free-market, globalization, capitalism, medical advancements, judicial protection are all aimed at maximizing this regulation over the individual’s life. In this new scenario death is not a favored option (Murray 197).

Hazel Marie Vitales then questioned this positive outlook on biopolitics since such regulation also produced negative results. War, racism, famine, ethnic cleansing and environmental crisis were pointed out as examples (162). Murray too talks about how the concept of ‘us against them’ develops where sacrificing the life of a few (inferior race or groups) is allowed to promote the well-being of the majority (198). But, environment crisis has now become a phenomenon where the entire population is exposed to life-threatening conditions. The reluctance of countries and governments to address deteriorating environmental condition is contrary to their theory of biopolitics. This paper then takes up the concept of necropolitics, as formulated by Achille Mbembe to explore how the meaning of sovereignty has undergone a change. Now individuals are exposed to the ‘threat of death’ constantly. Here then they are made to carry on their daily life in a ‘death-

world'. They thus become the 'living dead' without any power over themselves and their conditions (92).

Anagha Sivasakaran and Sayant Vijay traced the emergence of death-worlds under colonialism in the Malayalam novel by M. Mukundan titled, *On the Banks of the Mayyazhi* (1974). The novel depicts the shifts underwent by Mayyazhi town under French administration. Kurumbi Amma is a character shown as collaborating with the colonial setup while Dasan is depicted as a rebel (Sivasakaran and Vijay 54). Sivasakaran and Vijay point out that Kurumbi Amma symbolizes the colonised who are like slaves 'living a social death' without autonomy (55). They are being regulated and their identity is also being dictated by the colonial government. This leaves no space for resistance and the colonised internalizes the coloniser's view of them. Coming in contact with the colonizer everyday thus invokes the social death of the colonised. Hence, necropolitics in the form of lingering social death is employed by the coloniser to achieve sovereignty (Sivasakaran and Vijay 55).

Guy Emerson brought forth another perspective from the Mexican scenario where "bodies are always immersed in a violent death that infects all fields of knowledge beyond external constraints" (3). According to him the drug cartels of Mexico invoke fear, control and possibility of death by displaying dismembered corpses or engraving their insignia on them. The death-world enters the body and the living dead is forced to inhabit 'cartographies of violence' (3). Emerson noted how it slowly evolves into thanatopolitics where all bodies are rendered to be killable (5). Thanatopolitics then leads to the condition of 'physically wearing out of a population and the deterioration of people' (Emerson 5). It is an all-encompassing, nondiscriminatory politics of death—a politics that operates despite the limits of institutional power to inform living death" (Emerson 5). Taking cue from these studies this paper turns attention to how worsening air pollution is another death-world where each breath confers the status of living dead on a person's body. The aim is to look at the worsening human-nature

relation as depicted in the account by William Delisle Hay on the great London smog, titled, *Doom of the Great City; Being the Narrative of a Survivor, written A. D. 1942*(published in 1880).

The account starts with the celebration of the protagonist's eighty-fourth birthday with his family at New Zealand. It was upon his great-granddaughter's request that he finally decided to write down the 'great event' of his life. He admits how the thought of recalling the 'catastrophe' makes him to 'shudder'. Adding to this is the fact that this disaster took place on his birthday fifty-nine years back, because of which he "spend the night of the 2nd of February in prayer, in meditation, and in communion with Nature in her calmest and most peaceful aspects" (Hay 5). It is evident how the incident has left an everlasting impact on the narrator's mind and body. He then proceeds to explain his life in London, back in 1882, with his widowed mother and sister. After his father's demise he had to forego University for a living and was employed as a merchant's clerk. They lived in a basement of a building which he describes as "murky, dingy" and sighed at the fact that they had few friends. He compared his city life to the "hard labour of a prison" where he "endured constant torture of mind at the sight of my dear ones undergoing hardship, which, despite my most ardent efforts I was powerless to relieve" (Hay 8). The helplessness of the narrator to control the course of his life emerges here. City life is a sort of punishment for him as it alienated him from the countryside, nature and friends. He therefore labels London as "foul and rotten to the very core, and steeped in sin of every imaginable variety" (Hay 10). He identifies "vice and sin" as the "most cherished inhabitants" of London. The company of his mother and sister who rescued him from a complete social death was his only solace.

The account then shifts to the day of the tragedy, when the narrator was supposed to enjoy his time on a picnic with his friends. His mother and sister decided to stay back as the smog covering London intensified. He recalls how "the gas-lamps that were alight all day were wholly insufficient to penetrate the cloudy atmosphere

with their sickly lights” (Hay 21). He remembered that the London smoke arising from the consumption of coal carried poisonous substances as it was let out in the atmosphere without any filtering. “It filled the nostrils and air-passages of those who breathed with soot, and choked their throats and lungs with black, gritty particles, causing illness and often death to the aged, weakly and ailing” (Hay 22). So then every Londoner lived with death daily since breathing the poisonous air was fatal. The narrator notes how Londoners totally internalized their plight as they never looked into its causes and ways to improve the condition. He also blames the government for ignoring the persistent “nuisance” which was about to turn into a “grave evil.” Murray Bookchin’s observations become important here. He identified two kinds of shifts once the society became a class based one. He calls the first one material (coming of city, State, regulation, market economy) and the second one subjective (codes on morality, sexuality, values). He clubbed both under the term ‘epistemologies of rule’ which instilled a patriarchal egoistic morality in the ruler, while the ruled was trained for obedience at the ruler’s command (73). Slowly, the state became all powerful once the “personal loyalties are transmuted into depersonalized institutions, power becomes centralized and professionalized, custom gives way to law, and governance absorbs administration” (Bookchin 103). This is achieved through delegation of power enacted through the social contract which is “as an act of personal disempowerment, a conscious surrender by the self of control over the social conditions of life” (103). In Hay’s account too this surrendering is evident. The apathy continued despite the fact that there occurred accidents at rail, river and road because of low visibility. Meanwhile criminals turned this opportunity to carry out their deeds without being captured. The description thus fits the criteria of a death-world. Here all the bodies bear the mark of death by being an inhabitant of the city. The lingering smog is the greatest symbol of this death and everyday life is exposed to it. The sovereignty over one’s life is completely taken away as the vital exercise of breathing which sustains life becomes the biggest threat.

Things took a wild turn when the narrator overhears a passenger telling how people at Bermondsey locality were taken dead after inhaling the smog (Hay 24). After reaching his destination the narrator settled down with his hosts, the Forresters. The narrator brings up the incident from the train and one of the men, Dr. Wilton, explains how he once attended a case where a cab driver was brought dead after inhaling the London smog. The postmortem revealed that his clogged lungs resulted in suffocation leading to death. The men if at all they left the matter, were deeply disturbed and their distress turned into reality the next morning when they heard that almost five hundred lost their lives at Bermondsey. The three men set out to confirm the news and discovered that their locality was in a state of panic as all communication with London was cut off. People testified how those who went up to the City returned as they felt being choked. The testimonies grew grave once people narrated how bodies were lying everywhere. The narrator's remark over here is profound: "the fog drawn over midnight London an envelope of murky death, within whose awful fold all that had life had died" (Hay 36). Throughout his journey he described the violent death inflicted upon bodies invoking horror in himself and the guilt of not being able to take his dear ones with him. His state of powerlessness intensifies upon discovering the motionless bodies of his mother and sister. His account ends by reminding the "awful load of memory" he is carrying within him. Here then survival too doesn't hold much meaning since the memory reproduces the effect of death in him and transforms him into a 'living-dead' again.

If at all Hay's account is an imaginative piece it serves as a warning. Ecological degradation can cause huge loss to the present and future if left unattended. The question arises as to whether an alternative to the death-world is possible. Bookchin's concept of social ecology offers hope. He advocates moving away from the 'mechanistic' view of environmentalism that present plants, animals, minerals etc. as raw materials to fulfill human needs. Under this the cities become 'urban resources' and population gets labeled as 'human resources.' In environmentalism the goal is to

arrive at a form of truce and not to sustain the equilibrium between nature and human (Bookchin 21). Domination is the underlying principle here and an ecological approach corrects this in order to recognize the interdependency between living and non-living things. The fourth wave of ecocriticism then calls to recognize the ‘shared materiality between human and non-human’ aimed at ‘dissolving the human/nature binary’ (Marland 857). For Serenella Iovino there should be “an ecological horizontalism and extended moral imagination” (Marland 857). The Native American proverb thus underlines the need for such a change, that, “we do not inherit the Earth from our ancestors; we borrow it from our children.” Hence, addressing the human to human and human to nature relationship is the need of the hour.

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